

The Inkblots' Fall Into Controversy and its Exhumation; The Rorschach Test Remastered Using Modern Technologies and Innovations | A Review

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ABSTRACT

In 1921, the eponymous Hermann Rorschach created what would become one of the most illustrious and leveraged projective techniques in psychological assessment. The Rorschach Inkblot Test (RIT), or Rorschach Inkblot Method (RIM) has been an essential tool in understanding human cognition and diagnosing mental disorders; indeed at its time, it was considered a revolutionary development in the field. However, despite the test's unassailable historical significance, it has been the epicenter of recent criticism for its subjectivity and lack of standardized administration, dividing the community into a major controversy. With the tempest of controversy surrounding the topic, the frequency of use of the RIT has declined significantly. This research project aims to find how modern technologies and innovations have mitigated or repaired the original test's shortcomings. More specifically, how they have enhanced the accuracy, efficiency, accessibility, and utility of the Rorschach test, intending to restore its widespread use. The researchers primarily sourced information from APA PsycNet, using keywords such as "Rorschach technology" and "Modern Rorschach". After a review of the current literature, it was found that modern research and innovations in conjunction with technology advocate for reintroducing the Rorschach test in clinical settings. Their integration showed versatile capacities where the RIT excelled in each of the four aspects. The RIT's unique versatility and vast potential make it a tool too promising to leave as just a relic in the field of psychology.

Key Words: *Rorschach, Modern Rorschach, Technological innovations, Thematic Apperception Test, Projective psychological test*

1. INTRODUCTION

HERMANN RORSCHACH

Hermann Rorschach, born on November 8th, 1884, in Zürich, Switzerland, is the renowned creator of the inkblots used in the Rorschach Inkblot Test. The oldest of three children, Rorschach pursued a medical degree at the University of Zürich, practicing in the wake of figures with influential ideas on the subconscious, including Sigmund Freud. Drawing from multiple psychologists, predominantly Carl Jung, Rorschach became deeply interested in psychoanalysis, leading him to experiment with klecksography (inkblots) around 1918.

Previously, Rorschach is thought to have also studied the work of Szymon Hens, who had used inkblots on cards to discover his patients' deeper fantasies. Inspired by Hens' work, in 1918, Rorschach created scores of inkblots, ultimately refining 15 to use in his psychological assessments. During sessions, Rorschach would present these inkblots to patients and ask, "What might this be?"

Rorschach's pioneering work with inkblots and his systematic approach to interpreting responses laid the foundation for the Rorschach Inkblot test which ultimately became widely used for psychological evaluation and diagnosis. His vast contributions to psychology continue to influence the field, highlighting his innovative use of visual stimuli to explore the complexities of human cognition and emotion.

THE INKBLOT

Figure 1: One of Rorschach's most famous Inkblots. A patient would be shown a card with this blot and be asked to interpret it. From *NPR Choice page*. (2019). Npr.org. ([How Hermann Rorschach's 'Inkblots' Took On A Life Of Their Own](#))

The RIT is a projective psychological examination in which the patients' responses to ambiguous images (inkblots) are recorded and analyzed. Rorschach's aim was to allow the patient's subconscious to take hold and reveal itself by showing patients an ambiguous picture (See Figure 1). After asking "What might this be?" both their response and initial approach to answering the question would be evaluated. Rorschach's method was particularly aimed at diagnosing neuroticism, psychosis, or schizophrenia.

FAULTS WITHIN THE TEST

Today however, the RIT has become subject to significant controversy and consequently been phased out of the clinical setting, with the frequency of the Rorschach plummeting to 20% in North America (Viljoen et al., 2010). The argument opposed to the RIT centers on two primary schools of thought: One point argues that current media has distorted the perception of the RIT, misrepresenting it as strictly a personality test and often labeling it as a pseudoscience. These misconceptions have eroded its reputability, diminishing its standing in psychological assessment. The second, more pervasive critique concerns the test's subjectivity. Besides efforts to create a standardized form of evaluation of the RIT such as Exner (2002) and Holtzman (1968), the interpretation of RIT results has largely been up to the individual clinician. This creates differing diagnoses and difficulty in comparison- two ill-disposed qualities for a psychological tool. These two shortcomings are proving to be fatal to the RIT's success, however, once repaired, confidence in the test's validity could be repaired.

MODERN RIT INNOVATIONS

Modern technological capabilities have enabled researchers to improve upon the once-revolutionary test. Fields such as computational assistance, eye movement tracking, neuroimaging techniques, and machine learning have contributed to its restoration.

The application of computer technology in conjunction with the RIT holds promise for improving RIT administration in accuracy and efficiency by using uniform criteria for

evaluation. Using a fixed logic for evaluation facilitates standardized interpretations of assessment results, addressing the RIT's subjective interpretation while also improving reliability. Implementing eye movement tracking has improved test efficiency and utility by distinguishing subtleties in behavior to help diagnose conditions. Similarly, the integration of modern neuroscience techniques reveals brain function during the administration of the test. This improves the RIT's efficiency and accuracy by identifying specific neurological processes to aid in evaluation. Machine learning has improved the test's efficiency and utility through the leveraging of ML models in order to build algorithms for the assessment of the RIT and also in a cross-analysis capacity (McRae & John, 1992).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim of study

The goal of this study is to examine current advancements made to the RIT through modern technologies to assess the viability of reintroducing the test into clinical practice. More specifically, the objective is to assess improvements to the RIT's accuracy, efficiency, accessibility, and utility in order to ascertain the overall increase made to the RIT's efficacy. Alternatively, the researchers consider the possibility that the results contradict the hypothesis, which would solidify the RIT as solely a relic in the history of psychology.

2.2 Research Design

This paper consisted of an exploratory search focusing on identifying and reviewing modern innovations regarding the Rorschach test. The researchers conducted a comprehensive review of relevant existing literature; a basis of relevancy required that the article discussed advancements using modern technology to the RIT or other similar projective tests. A total of 28 articles were found that fit the criteria relating to modern technological innovations regarding the RIT.

2.3 Hypothesis

The driving hypothesis postulates that modern innovations to the Rorschach Inkblot Test, to administration or evaluation, have sufficiently improved the Rorschach test in terms of accuracy,

efficiency, accessibility, or utility, justifying its restored widespread utilization in clinical settings.

2.4 Consent & Ethical Considerations

Relevant ethical considerations were followed including providing correct references, taking bias into consideration, and a holistic review of the literature.

2.5 Scales/tools used/instruments used

Research was primarily conducted online via computer or laptop with supplementary materials obtained through in-person visits to libraries. Any research not pertaining to the Rorschach test in either administration or evaluation using modern technologies was omitted. Articles were selected based on their innovative insights and effectiveness in leveraging mode.

2.6 Data Collection Procedure

In order to find newer iterations of the Rorschach Inkblot Test (RIT) a thorough literature review from sources including Britannica, APA psycnet, and the NIH was conducted. Key terms including “*Modern Rorschach Test*”, “*Rorschach innovations*”, and “*Rorschach technology*” were used initially to gather relevant studies. Subsequently, the search was refined using more specific words including “*Rorschach eye tracking*”, “*Rorschach neurology*”, “*Rorschach computer*” and “*Rorschach machine learning*”. Sources that did not fit these specific topics were either integrated into the discussion or excluded completely.

Four main categories of research were found: 1) Computational analysis of Rorschach test. 2) The use of neuroscience and neuroimaging during administration 3) The tracking of patients’ facial cues such as eye movement during administration. 4) The use of the Rorschach in conjunction with machine learning or artificial intelligence.

Although articles that disputed the use of the RIT appeared, it seemed that there was a consensus acknowledging the potential the Rorschach test holds and its ongoing relevance in psychological assessment. As one of the most extensively researched psychological tests in history, there was ample work to review.

3. RESULTS

Innovations in the RIT stem from various fields, with four main categories: computational assistance, tracking eye movement, neuroimaging and neuroscience tools, and machine learning (ML). Each labeled category leverages modern technologies that have become available relatively recently, contributing significantly to the evolution of the RIT. These innovations underscore the integration of cutting-edge technologies into psychological assessment, reshaping how the RIT is administered, interpreted, and utilized in clinical practice

Table 1. provides a visual template of the 4 categories, organized by consecutive order. To the right is an elaboration on the applications of these innovations, which will be further explored.

Table 1. An overview of the innovations found from researching scientific databases.

Innovation	Application
Computational assistance	Computers administering, Computational analysis, Algorithmic deployment
Tracking of eye movement	Tracking of eye movement, saccadic response, white area response
Neuroimaging and neuroscience tools	Neuroimaging such as fMRI, EEG, and other radio wave scans of the brain
Machine learning models	Machine learning models (ML), natural language processing (NLP), Gaussian mixture models (Gmm)

Computational assistance:

Computational assistance involves the use of computers or other algorithms to administrate or evaluate the RIT in order to increase accuracy, and accessibility (Banerjee & R, 1983). Integrating computers with the RIT represents a logical next step to reduce subjective components that undermine the technique. Standardized evaluation criteria such as the

Rorschach Performance Assessment System (R-PAS) and the Comprehensive System (CS) developed by Exner (2002), enhance objectivity and facilitate comparisons between psychologists.

The use of computers allows less experienced clinicians to administer the Rorschach with the same degree of accuracy as seasoned professionals, increasing the test's accessibility. It also establishes a standardized evaluation process that ensures consistency and reliability in scoring the RIT.

The earliest experiments with computers and the Rorschach coincided with the computer's inception. However, of the 4 topics, the literature found on this subject tended to be older, predominantly including articles from the 1960s to 1980s. This was likely due to the surge of computer culture in America and the apex of the RIT's popularity also during that period.

For example, Piotrowski (1964) pioneered computer-based evaluation methods for the RIT, focusing on identifying schizophrenia through data interpretation. His work involved feeding patients' RIT responses into a computer, which were compartmentalized and evaluated, and output a response accordingly. The output listed if the patient ultimately had schizophrenic or non-schizophrenic tendencies. Ross (1967) similarly automated data collection, scoring, and evaluation processes, demonstrating the feasibility of objective, algorithmic evaluation of the RIT without the need for direct human oversight. Even before Ross, Gorham (1967) used Holtzman Inkblot technique (HIT) variables to categorize responses. The HIT is an attempt at a standardized form of the RIT based upon a set of 22 variables, including location, anatomy, hostility, or anxiety (Holtzman, 1968). These variables helped replicate how actual psychologists interpret responses.

The computer programs' abilities to perform the task pose serious questions regarding the psychologist's role in conducting the RIT. It is worth noting that some psychologists such as Piotrowski, believed that computers are not meant to replace the psychologist. Others such as Exner believed that computers cannot duplicate the complex, and nuanced process of a real clinician. Exner played a revolutionary role in the development of the Rorschach and created empirical systems to score the test. Computers show huge promise in increasing the efficiency, accuracy, and accessibility of the Rorschach task, by reducing subjective components and establishing standardized rules of evaluation.

Tracking of eye movement:

Tracking eye movement encompasses all motion of the eye and other abnormal cues. This technique is useful in order to illuminate explanations to certain responses during the RIT and for identifying signs of psychological conditions - increasing the efficiency and utility of the original test (Thomas, 1963). Eye-tracking data also provides deeper insights that reinforce Rorschach principles and allow for more comprehensive information extraction.

Holzman (1989) first noted abnormalities in smooth eye movement (movement of the eyes fixated on an object) during the administration of the RIT. However, in 1989 Holzman was restricted by the infancy of eye-tracking technology and could not explore the subject more deeply. Biometric eye tracking technology matured around the 1980s when the technology became reliably accurate and computers could handle the data load. Today, eye tracking is an integral part of the biomedical field and is consistently utilized (Sqalli et al., 2023). Devices such as the eyelink 1000 Plus, an apparatus that follows a patient's gaze at a computer screen, are used to track and log movements.

Eye-tracking has been employed to reveal varying aspects related to the RIT: how visual stimuli can signal signs of schizophrenia (Hori et al., 2002); how eye movement relates to increased cognitive function while taking the RIT (Ales et al., 2019); how white space correlates to different responses during the RIT (Ales et al., 2021); and the correlation between saccadic responses and the Rorschach (Dauphin et al., 2023). These findings demonstrate that eye movement is significantly related to thematic apperception tests such as the RIT. They advocate for the continued use of eye tracking in tandem with the administration of the RIT.

Neuroimaging and other neurological tools:

Neuroimaging includes the use of brain scans or any other tool to image the brain. Similar to the tracking of eye movement, imaging of the brain during testing could reveal further explanations of how patients process the test (Acklin & Wu-Holt, 1996). This would illuminate the actual neurological processing and comprehension of the RIT, allowing for a faster, more extensive evaluation and data on the RIT- enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of RIT evaluation.

Neuroimaging with the RIT is typically administered using functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), which highlights cortical regions in use by measuring changes in blood flow associated with brain function. Alternatively, studies also used electroencephalography (EEG)

which measures electrical activity within the brain. The fMRI specifically is a relatively new technology, in clinical use only for the last 4 decades. Despite its infancy, it has since revolutionized the field and allowed for countless advancements, such as its application to the RIT (Bigler, 2017).

In multiple instances, Girimoni tests theories assumed about the RIT. Girimoni et al. (2017) found, through fMRI scans, that participants who took the RIT showed high levels of visual processing as well as strong associations of emotion and emotional memory recall- reinforcing traditional thoughts on the test. Vitolo et al. (2020) investigated the validity of the correlation between eye tracking with the Rorschach by using FMRI data and confirmed its accuracy. Girimoni et al. (2019), tested an important assumption concerning the RIT's efficacy- that Rorschach responses replicate real-life processes and behaviors. After evaluating fMRI data he confirms its validity. Finally, Porcelli et al. (2013) confirmed that variable M (Human movement) has a neurological basis by analyzing EEG data, important for the continued use of the variable.

Vecchio et al. (2023) conducted a holistic investigation of correlations between underlying neurological processes and psychopathology markers. He summarized the use of EEG, functional near-infrared spectroscopy (FNIRIS), which uses near-infrared light to measure levels of hemoglobin, and fMRI scans to be promising and enlightening of the visual, emotional, and social comprehension of the RIT.

Machine learning models:

Machine learning, which includes the utilization of AI and other Machine learning (ML) models in any capacity with the Rorschach, shows the potential to increase the RIT's accuracy, efficiency, and utility (Whitehouse, 2019). This is possible through using ML to develop algorithms for the RIT, using it in administration and other cross-analysis capacities. These capacities increase algorithms' effectiveness and evolve the test beyond its traditional usage.

Machine learning is a field that focuses on the development of statistical algorithms that autonomously learn from gathered data and information. Conceived as a late byproduct of the computer revolution, ML is close to its genesis (Kononenko, 2001); as a result, the research and existing literature on this topic is the least prominent of the four categories. However, considerable research still exists focusing on the integration of ML and RIT.

Researchers employed ML in a variety of capacities in conjunction with the RIT. Ponzi et al. (2022) used Gaussian mixture models (GMM) and expectation maximization (EM) to cluster data and evaluate RIT data. GMM helps to identify patterns within the clustered data, while EM is an iterative approach for maximum likelihood estimation. These tools enhance the efficiency of the evaluation of the RIT by more quickly identifying trends and correlations that might be missed by human evaluations. ML models have also been used to evaluate other projective tests similar to the RIT such as the five-factor model by McCrae & John (1992) or Camati & F. Enembreck (2020). Armañanzas et al. (2013) and Bornstein (2022) also used RIT data to validate ML models that evaluate traits similar to Rorschach variables (Exner, 2002). This cross-analysis use of the Rorschach increases its utility, making it a more versatile tool in psychological assessment.

4. DISCUSSION

The original aim driving this study posits that current modern innovations towards the Rorschach Inkblot Test (RIT) have sufficiently enhanced the test in terms of accuracy, efficiency, accessibility, or utility, justifying its broader use in assessing psychological conditions.

Our findings support this hypothesis. Research on the newest uses of technology to modernize the RIT in its administration, categorization, and evaluation, shows that there are ample developments to the RIT to warrant its place in the clinical setting. Our review indicates that by leveraging modern technology, these innovations have addressed shortcomings such as subjectivity and reliability in the original test while remaining true to Hermann Rorschach's original inspiration (Vigilone & Hilsenroth, 2001). However, misconceptions in today's world surrounding the RIT hinder the Rorschach test's growth, commonly misconceived to be strictly a personality test or even a pseudoscience. Its portrayal in modern media and the proliferation of inkblot images also combats the RIT's efficacy because it reduces original thought during test administration (Bushley, 2015).

The original hypothesis is supported by improvements in efficiency, accessibility, accuracy, and utility from 4 major advancements to the RIT: computational assistance, eye movement tracking, neuroimaging, and machine learning. The addition of computational assistance established objective algorithmic evaluations of RIT responses, improving the task's accuracy and

accessibility by creating standardized results to address Rorschach's issue of subjectivity (Exner, 1987). It also enables less experienced psychologists to administer the test, making the test a much more accessible tool requiring less specialized faculty (Ross, 1968). Eye-tracking technology has increased the RIT's efficiency by revealing deeper insights into patients' responses to the RIT, and even detecting psychopathological conditions including schizophrenia (Ales et al., 2019; Hori et al., 2002). The benefits of efficiency are apparent, not only in labor and cost saving but also in urgent cases where time is critical. Neuroimaging has enhanced the test's efficiency in a similar way by illuminating patients' cognitive comprehension of the test allowing for faster, more comprehensive evaluations (Vechio et al., 2023); additionally, it has aided in reinforcing the RIT's scientific basis (Girmonini et al., 2017). Researchers have used machine learning to increase the RIT's utility and accuracy by leveraging it for the creation of algorithms to evaluate RIT data (Ponzi et al., 2022). Conversely, researchers used RIT data in a cross-analysis capacity to validate ML models (Armañanzas et al., 2013). By using the RIT for more than clinical evaluations, the researchers expand the RIT. These findings strongly support the re-introduction of the RIT in professional settings.

5. CONCLUSION

This study explored whether the Rorschach Inkblot Test has been sufficiently developed in terms of efficiency, utility, accessibility, and accuracy with modern technology, to determine if it deserves its place in the clinical setting. The Rorschach test has recently faced significant criticism, reducing its frequency of assessing psychological conditions. However, contemporary literature shows many innovations that not only address its shortcomings but have also enhanced it in alternate aspects.

The results of this study indicate that technological advancements, such as eye tracking, the introduction of neuroimaging tools such as fMRIs and EEGs, the use of computers and digital algorithms, and the utilization of ML have advanced the Rorschach Inkblot Test's accessibility, efficiency, utility, and accuracy making the assessment a tool worth reincorporating into the field of psychology. Though some gaps continue to exist, the advancements thus far are significant and warrant further consideration. The accumulation of promising findings towards innovations

of the RIT connotes that further research on the intersection of modern technology and the Rorschach Test or other similar projective tests would continue to elevate their success.

6. LIMITATIONS

The abundant existing research on the Rorschach Inkblot Test (RIT) provided a solid foundation for this study. However, certain areas, such as the intersection of machine learning and the Rorschach, were niche and limited due to the relative infancy of the field, making it challenging to gain a complete overview. On a broader scale, most categories had ample research available, allowing for a comprehensive review. Overall the research conducted was thorough, resulting in a comprehensive review of the subject.

REFERENCES

- Acklin, M. W., & Wu-Holt, P. (1996). Contributions of Cognitive Science to the Rorschach Technique: Cognitive and Neuropsychological Correlates of the Response Process. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 67(1), 169–178.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa6701_13
- Ales, F., Giromini, L., Bosi, J., & Zennaro, A. (2022). White space responses in the Rorschach: Using eye-tracking to further understand the distinction between space reversal and space integration. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02632-4>
- Ales, F., Giromini, L., & Zennaro, A. (2019). *Complexity and cognitive engagement in the rorschach task: An eye-tracking study*. Psycnet.apa.org.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2019-22044-001>
- Applications & History Of Eye Tracking Technology*. (n.d.). Gazepoint.
<https://www.gazept.com/eye-tracking/?v=7516fd43adaa>
- Areh, I., Verklempt, F., & Allan, A. (2021). Critical review of the use of the Rorschach in European courts. *Psychiatry, Psychology and Law*, 29(2), 1–23.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13218719.2021.1894260>
- Armañanzas, R., Alonso-Nanclares, L., DeFelipe-Oroquieta, J., Kastanauskaite, A., de Sola, R. G., DeFelipe, J., Bielza, C., & Larrañaga, P. (2013). Machine Learning Approach for the

- Outcome Prediction of Temporal Lobe Epilepsy Surgery. *PLoS ONE*, 8(4), e62819.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0062819>
- Banerjee, S., & R, K. (1983). Computer model of scoring of Rorschach responses. *Indian Statistical Institute*, 28(1), 51–55. Institutional Repository.
- Bigler, E. D. (2017). Structural neuroimaging in neuropsychology: History and contemporary applications. *Neuropsychology*, 31(8), 934–953. <https://doi.org/10.1037/neu0000418>
- Bornstein, R. F. (2022). Toward an integrative perspective on the person. *Rorschachiana*, 43(2), 103–127. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1192-5604/a000160>
- Bushey, M. A. (2015). Rorschach Inkblot Invasion of Pop Culture. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 172(10), 949–949. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2015.15040519>
- Butcher, J., Perry, J., & Dean, B. (2009). *Oxford Handbook of Personality Assessment 10 Computer-Based Assessment*.
https://dpl6hyzg28thp.cloudfront.net/media/Computer_based_assessment.pdf
- Camati, R. S., & F. Enembreck. (). TextBased Automatic Personality Recognition: a Projective Approach. *2020 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, 218–225. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SMC42975.2020.9282859>
- Costantino, G., Flanagan, R., & Malgady, R. (1995). The History of the Rorschach: Overcoming Bias in Multicultural Projective Assessment. *Rorschachiana*, 20(1), 148–171.
<https://doi.org/10.1027/1192-5604.20.1.148>
- Dauphin, B., & Greene, H. H. (2012). Here’s Looking at You. *Rorschachiana*, 33(1), 3–22.
<https://doi.org/10.1027/1192-5604/a000025>
- Dauphin, B., Greene, H. H., Juve, M., Boyle, M., & Day-Suba, E. (2023). Transforming Psychological Testing With Saccadic Responses: Internal Consistency is High for Rorschach and Facial Expressions. *Sagepub*, 130 (5).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00315125231188564>
- Drayton, M. (2012, July 24). What’s behind the Rorschach inkblot test? *BBC News*.
<https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-18952667>
- Exner, J. (1987). Computer assistance in Rorschach interpretation. *British Journal of Projective Psychology*, 32(1), 2–19. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1988-26597-001>
- Exner, J. (2002). *The Rorschach: A comprehensive system, 4th ed.* (4th ed., p. 704).
<https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2003-06359-000>

- Giromini, L., Viglione, D. J., Vitolo, E., Cauda, F., & Zennaro, A. (2019). Introducing the concept of neurobiological foundation of Rorschach responses using the example of Oral Dependent Language. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, *60*(6), 528–538.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/sjop.12585>
- Giromini, L., Viglione, D. J., Zennaro, A., & Cauda, F. (2017). Neural activity during production of rorschach responses: An fMRI study. *Psychiatry Research: Neuroimaging*, *262*, 25–31.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychresns.2017.02.001>
- Gorham, D. R. (1967). Validity and reliability studies of a computer-based scoring system for inkblot responses. *Journal of Consulting Psychology*, *31*(1), 65–70.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/h0020980>
- Holtzman, W. H. (1968). Holtzman Inkblot Technique. *Springer EBooks*, 136–170.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-39575-2_6
- Holzman, P. S. (1989). The use of eye movement dysfunctions in exploring the genetic transmission of schizophrenia. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Neurological Sciences*, *239*(1), 43–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf01739743>
- HORI, Y., HIROSHI FUKUZAKO, SUGIMOTO, Y., & MORIKUNI TAKIGAWA. (2002). Eye movements during the Rorschach test in schizophrenia. *Psychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences*, *56*(4), 409–418. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1440-1819.2002.01030.x>
- Kononenko, I. (2001). Machine learning for medical diagnosis: history, state of the art and perspective. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, *23*(1), 89–109.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0933-3657\(01\)00077-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0933-3657(01)00077-x)
- McCrae, R. R., & John, O. P. (1992). An introduction to the five-factor model and its applications. *Journal of Personality*, *60*(2), 175–215.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.1992.tb00970.x>
- Meyer, G. J. (2017). What Rorschach performance can add to assessing and understanding personality. *International Journal of Personality Psychology*, *3*(1), 36–49.
- Mihura, J. L., Meyer, G. J., Bombel, G., & Dumitrascu, N. (2015). Standards, accuracy, and questions of bias in Rorschach meta-analyses: Reply to Wood, Garb, Nezworski, Lilienfeld, and Duke (2015). *Psychological Bulletin*, *141*(1), 250–260.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038445>

- Mohammed Tahri Sqalli, Begali Aslonov, Mukhammadjon Gafurov, Nurmukhammad Mukhammadiev, & Yahya Sqalli Houssaini. (2023). Eye tracking technology in medical practice: a perspective on its diverse applications. *Frontiers in Medical Technology*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmedt.2023.1253001>
- NPR Choice page. (2019). Npr.org. <https://www.npr.org/sections/health-shots/2017/02/17/515449428/how-hermann-rorschach-inks-inkblots-took-on-a-life-of-their-own>
- Piotrowski, Z. A. (1964). *DIGITAL-COMPUTER INTERPRETATION OF INKBLOT TEST DATA*. <https://dpl6hyzg28thp.cloudfront.net/media/BF01573364.pdf>
- Ponzi, V., Russo, S., & Napoli, C. (2022). Analysis pre and post covid-19 pandemic rorschach test data of using em algorithms and gmm models. *IRIS*, 55–63.
- Poppen, R. L., Pribram, K. H., & Robinson, R. S. (1965). Effects of frontal lobotomy in man on the performance of a multiple choice task. *Experimental Neurology*, 11(2), 217–229. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-4886\(65\)90014-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-4886(65)90014-2)
- Porcelli, P., Giromini, L., Parolin, L., Pineda, J. A., & Viglione, D. J. (2013). Mirroring Activity in the Brain and Movement Determinant in the Rorschach Test. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 95(5), 444–456. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223891.2013.775136>
- Ross, D. (1968). Elsevier Journal of School Psychology Volume 6, Issue 3, Spring 1968, Pages 200-205 Journal of School Psychology Computer processing of inkblot test data. *Journal of School Psychology*, 6(3), 200–205. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4405\(68\)90016-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4405(68)90016-2)
- Teles Filho, R. V. (2020). Hermann Rorschach: From klecksography to psychiatry. *Dementia & Neuropsychologia*, 14(1), 80–82. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-57642020dn14-010013>
- The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica. (2018). Rorschach test . In *Encyclopædia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/science/Rorschach-Test>
- Thomas, E. L. (1963). Eye Movements and Fixations during Initial Viewing of Rorschach Cards. *Journal of Projective Techniques and Personality Assessment*, 27(3), 345–353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0091651x.1963.10120058>
- Vecchio, A., Roberti, E., Pulido, S. G., Orlandi, M., Provenzi, L., & Mensi, M. (2023). Only an inkblot? A literature review of the neural correlates of the Rorschach inkblot test. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 152, 105281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2023.105281>

- Viglione, D. J., & Hilsenroth, M. J. (2001). The Rorschach: facts, fictions, and future. *Psychological Assessment, 13*(4), 452–471. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11793891/>
- Viljoen, J. L., McLachlan, K., & Vincent, G. M. (2010). Assessing violence risk and psychopathy in juvenile and adult offenders: A survey of clinical practices. *Assessment, 17*(3), 377–395. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073191109359587>
- Vitolo, E., Giromini, L., Viglione, D. J., Cauda, F., & Zennaro, A. (2020). Complexity and Cognitive Engagement in the Rorschach Task: An fMRI Study. *Journal of Personality Assessment, 103*(5), 634–644. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223891.2020.1842429>
- Whitehouse, J. (2019). The Rorschach in the 21st century: A tablet-based administration equivalence study. *William James College ProQuest Dissertations & Theses*.